

On a Solution to the Dirac Equation with a Triangular Potential Well

Renebeth B. Payod¹ and Vasil A. Saroka^{2, 3, 4, a)}

¹⁾*Institute of Physics, University of the Philippines, College, Los Baños, Laguna, 4031 Philippines*

²⁾*Department of Physics, University of Rome Tor Vergata and INFN, Via della Ricerca Scientifica 1, Roma 00133, Italy*

³⁾*Institute for Nuclear Problems, Belarusian State University, Bobruiskaya 11, 220030 Minsk, Belarus*

⁴⁾*TBpack Ltd., 27 Old Gloucester Street, London, WC1N 3AX, United Kingdom*

(*Electronic mail: vasil.saroka@roma2.infn.it)

(*Electronic mail: rbpayod@up.edu.ph)

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Chiral anomalies resulting from the breaking of classical symmetries at the quantum level are fundamental to quantum field theory and gaining ever-growing importance in the description of topological materials in condensed matter physics. Here we present analytical solutions of the Dirac equation for massless $3 + 1$ fermions confined to an infinite stripe and placed into a background gauge field forming a triangular potential well across the width of the stripe. Such an effective $1 + 1$ system hosts zero-energy modes resulting in the gauge field-dependent chiral anomaly structure. This problem has a direct relation to a half-bearded graphene nanoribbon placed into an in-plane external electric field and offers it an exact solution in terms of new special functions that are similar but not reducible to Airy functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The behavior of electrons in triangular potential wells is described by fundamental solutions known as Airy function^{1,2}. Airy functions play an important role in accurately modeling charge carrier properties within two-dimensional electron gases semiconductor devices^{3,4}. Understanding electronic transport in semiconductor heterostructures is crucial for designing advanced optoelectronic devices.

At the turn of the century, an increasing number of exact solutions to the Schrödinger equation has been reported by using both conventional approach^{5,6} and factorization of supersymmetric quantum mechanics (SUSY)^{7,8}. Likewise, other solvable systems with exact solutions to the Schrödinger equation have been shown in the bound states of a hyperbolic double-well potential⁹ and hyperbolic asymmetric double well potential¹⁰. Generally, the analytic solutions to the Schrödinger equation were obtained through reduction to a hypergeometric equation¹¹ or by Heun's differential equation^{9,10,12,13}.

Exact solutions of the relativistic Dirac equation supplemented with various background potentials is being a subject of great interest too¹⁴⁻²². Approximate and exact analytical solutions have been reported for a number of cases, including linear scalar and vector potentials²¹. Some of these analytical solutions reduce to Bessel and Airy functions²².

At the low energy limit in condensed matter systems, the Schrödinger equation manifests as a Dirac equation^{23,24}. In two dimensions this happens around degeneracy points in the energy bands, topologically acting as the Berry curvature sources in k -space and resembling Dirac monopoles²⁵⁻²⁷. The Berry curvature monopoles in graphene are the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' Dirac points. The effective Dirac equation of graphene is capable to describe the electronic properties of graphene nanoribbons (GNR) with different edge structures, such as the prominent zigzag and armchair edge geometries^{28,29}. Despite previous studies done on the edge states and flat bands of graphene nanoribbons³⁰⁻³⁸, a Dirac equation based description is lacking for a GNR known as the half-bearded graphene nanoribbon (hbGNR). Here, we present an analytical treatment of the Dirac equation motivated by hbGNRs and their prominent zero-energy modes³⁶⁻³⁹. We consider a more general case accounting also the influence of an external in-plane electric field as depicted in Fig. 1(a). This problem is equivalent to the Stark effect that has been considered for armchair graphene nanoribbons⁴⁰.

We report here a new set of special functions R and V in the solution of the Dirac equation, which are somewhat analogous but not reducible to the Airy functions. Using a series of substitutions and the power series method, we demonstrate that an exact solution to the Dirac equation relevant to hbGNRs subjected in an external in-plane electric field can be achieved. By combining these analytical solutions with the appropriate boundary conditions, a dispersion equation can be constructed. The dispersion reveals a field-dependent $1+1$ chiral anomaly.

^{a)}<https://sites.google.com/view/vasilsaroka/home>; <https://www.tbpack.co.uk/>

FIG. 1. (a) A honeycomb lattice confined to a half-bearded ribbon by cuts normally to x -axis at $\pm L/2$ - hbGNR. Large black arrow shows the direction of the applied in-plane electric field F . Gray dashed rectangle is the honeycomb lattice unit cell with two basis atoms (sublattices) denoted as A and B. (b) Gauge field dependent chiral anomaly structure of the energy bands $n = 0$.

II. ANALYTICAL SOLUTIONS FOR CONFINED MASSLESS DIRAC FERMIONS COUPLED TO A GAUGE FIELD.

We aim to formulate the problem in its most general Lagrangian form to potentially extend its application beyond its original scope. We start from the action of a massless fermion in $3 + 1$ space-time, $x = (ct, x, y, z)$, coupled to a gauge field:

$$S = \int d^4x \mathcal{L} = \int d^4x \bar{\Psi} i \gamma^\mu D_\mu \Psi, \quad (1)$$

where covariant derivative $D_\mu = \partial_\mu + iqA_\mu$, with $A_\mu = (\varphi, A_x, A_y, A_z)$ being a gauge field represented by 4-vector of the electromagnetic field, q includes the sign of the charge, and the summation over repeated index $\mu = 0, 1, 2, 3$ is implied. We choose $A_\mu = (xF, 0, 0, 0)$, where F is the strength of the electromagnetic field, and $q = -1$ is coupling to the electromagnetic field for the electron. γ^μ are the Dirac matrices obeying Clifford algebra $Cl(1, 3)$: $\{\gamma^\mu, \gamma^\nu\} = 2\eta^{\mu\nu} I_{4 \times 4}$, where $\eta^{\mu\nu}$ is the space-time metric with the signature fixed to $\eta^{\mu\nu} = \text{diag}(1, -1, -1, -1)$ and $I_{4 \times 4}$ is the 4×4 unity matrix. As obtained by Taylor expansion of the tight-binding Hamiltonian in graphene^{28,41}, we set the Dirac γ -matrices representation in terms of Pauli matrices, the σ_x , σ_y and σ_z , and 2×2 unit matrix I as follows:

$$\gamma^0 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\sigma_y \\ -\sigma_y & 0 \end{pmatrix}; \quad \gamma^1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & i\sigma_z \\ i\sigma_z & 0 \end{pmatrix}; \quad \gamma^2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -I \\ I & 0 \end{pmatrix}; \quad \gamma^3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i\sigma_x \\ -i\sigma_x & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

The $\bar{\Psi} = \Psi^\dagger \gamma^0$ in Eq. (1) is a Dirac adjoint. By minimizing the action in Eq. (1), we arrive at the Lagrange-Euler equations of motion for a quantum field⁴². For a given Lagrangian, this result leads to the standard Dirac equation in covariant form: $i\gamma^\mu D_\mu \Psi = 0$. Multiplying this equation from the right by γ^0 , we transition to the Hamiltonian form of the Dirac equation in terms of Dirac matrices $\vec{\alpha} = \gamma^0 \gamma^i$, $i = 1, 2, 3$, and $\beta = \gamma^0$: $i\partial\Psi/\partial t = \mathcal{H}\Psi$, where

$$\mathcal{H} = \vec{\alpha} \vec{\kappa} - I_{4 \times 4} \cdot xF = \begin{pmatrix} H_{\mathbf{K}} & 0 \\ 0 & H_{\mathbf{K}'} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

with $\kappa_{x,y,z} = -i\partial_{x,y,z}$. We explicitly write the matrices $\vec{\alpha}$ and β as

$$\alpha_x = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_x \end{pmatrix}; \quad \alpha_y = \begin{pmatrix} -\sigma_y & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_y \end{pmatrix}; \quad \alpha_z = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_z & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_z \end{pmatrix}; \quad \beta = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\sigma_y \\ -\sigma_y & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where they obey the following relations: $\alpha_i^2 = \beta^2 = I_{4 \times 4}$; $\{\alpha_i, \beta\} = 0$; $\{\alpha_i, \alpha_j\} = \delta_{ij} I_{4 \times 4}$, for $i, j = 1, 2, 3$. The 4×4 Hamiltonian \mathcal{H} features two chiral sectors or valleys denoted as \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' . If we define $\gamma^5 = -i\gamma^0 \gamma^1 \gamma^2 \gamma^3$, which anti-commutes with all γ -matrices and squares to unity matrix⁴³:

$$\gamma^5 = \begin{pmatrix} -I & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

then the chiral projector $P = (I_{4 \times 4} \pm \gamma^5) / 2$ is a valley projector. If the 4-component bispinor is an eigenvector of the defined chiral operator γ^5 , $\gamma^5 \Psi = \pm \Psi$, then it is also an eigenvector of $H = P \mathcal{H} P^\dagger$. Since H is effectively a 2×2 Hamiltonian, the bispinor is essentially a 2-component spinor $\Psi = (\phi_A, \phi_B)^T$, where instead of regular spin up and down components, we use a honeycomb lattice sublattice components A and B [see Fig. 1(a)]. Thus, our initial problem with 4 equations decays into 2 independent problems with 2 equations each. Finally, we confine our massless fermion to xy -plane, i.e. $\Psi(x, y, z, t) \equiv \Psi(x, y, t)$ so that $\kappa_z \Psi(x, y, t) = 0$, and impose hard-wall boundary condition on the spinor Ψ along x -axis in both chiral sectors, i.e. valleys \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' :

$$(I - \sigma_z) \Psi|_{x=\pm L/2} = 0, \quad (6)$$

where L is the size of the stripe which to fermions are confined. Now, fermions here are free to move only perpendicular to the field F along y -axis, such that we have $\Psi(x, y, t) = \Psi(x) \exp[ik_y y - i\epsilon t]$ and the system turns effectively into $1 + 1$ space-time.

The two 2×2 time-independent Dirac equations for $\Psi(x)$ read:

$$(-i\sigma_x \partial_x \mp \sigma_y k_y - Fx) \Psi = \epsilon \Psi, \quad (7)$$

where the upper and lower signs of $\sigma_y k_y$ identify the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' valleys, respectively. We then examine the expression of the spinors at the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' point. By multiplying both side of Eq. (7) by $i\sigma_x$, we get

$$(\partial_x \pm \sigma_z k_y - i\sigma_x(Fx + \epsilon)) \Psi = 0 \quad (8)$$

with the upper and lower signs of the $\sigma_z k_y$ designate the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' valleys, respectively. Starting here, we use the upper and lower signs in each equation to denote the k_y sign assignments on the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' valleys. It is evident that the external field F shows a term proportional to σ_x , resulting to a sublattice mixing within the system. In terms of the spinor components $\phi_{A,B}$, the set of equations take an explicit form of:

$$\partial_x \phi_A \pm k_y \phi_A - i(\epsilon + Fx) \phi_B = 0, \quad (9)$$

$$\partial_x \phi_B \mp k_y \phi_B - i(\epsilon + Fx) \phi_A = 0. \quad (10)$$

When $\epsilon + Fx = 0$ and $k_y \neq 0$, we get the flat "zero"-energy modes which will be shown later in section III B. We then consider a new variable $\alpha = \epsilon + Fx$ and let this $\alpha \neq 0$. Starting from Eq. (10), we can express ϕ_A as $\phi_A = (\partial_x \phi_B \mp k_y \phi_B) / (i\alpha)$ and substitute this expression into Eq. (9). This yields the following equation for the spinor component ϕ_B :

$$\partial_{xx} \phi_B - \frac{F}{\alpha} \partial_x \phi_B \pm \left(\frac{F}{\alpha} k_y \mp k_y^2 \pm \alpha^2 \right) \phi_B = 0. \quad (11)$$

Next, we introduce a change of the independent variable, $\xi = \alpha/F = \epsilon/F + x$, into Eq. (11) that results to:

$$\partial_{\xi\xi} \phi_B - \frac{1}{\xi} \partial_\xi \phi_B \pm \left(\frac{k_y}{\xi} \mp k_y^2 \pm F^2 \xi^2 \right) \phi_B = 0 \quad (12)$$

with the upper and lower signs for the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' valleys, respectively. Setting the boundary conditions according to Eq. (6) yields $\phi_B(\xi_1) = 0$ and $\phi_B(\xi_2) = 0$, where $\xi_1 = (\epsilon/F) + (L/2)$ and $\xi_2 = (\epsilon/F) - (L/2)$.

This Eq. (12) is a second order differential equation where the singular points can be found at $\xi = 0$ and $\xi = \infty$. The nature of these two singularities comprises a regular singular point at $\xi = 0$ and an irregular singular point at $\xi = \infty$. Hence, Eq. (12) resembles a Bessel equation, which represents a special case of a hypergeometric equation with three regular poles, where two regular poles have merged leading to the irregular singularity. We can then employ the power series method⁴⁴ to obtain a solution of Eq. (12) around the remaining regular singular point $\xi = 0$.

The power series method seeks to find a solution to a differential equation using an infinite power series expansion of the form $S = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \xi^n$, establishing a recursive relationship between the series coefficients a_n 's. Applying directly this method to Eq. (12) fails due to a wide range of terms leading to a power series with largely shifted degrees of ξ 's. To reduce the power series, we can isolate the terms and set the first 4 coefficients to zero in the final series. Unfortunately, this process disrupts the recursive relation between a_n coefficients.

To address this issue, we aim to simplify the components in the Eq. (12) by eliminating terms within $((k_y/\xi) \mp k_y^2 \pm F^2 \xi^2) \phi_B$. We can take a function $\phi_B(\xi) = u(\xi) \exp(\pm k_y \xi)$ to remove the terms k_y^2 and k_y/ξ , where "+" is for the \mathbf{K} valley while "-" is for the \mathbf{K}' valley. From a physical standpoint, this substitution can be interpreted as a limiting solution under a zero external field $F = 0$ or an equivalent large k_y limit for $F \neq 0$. This substitution results in:

$$\partial_{\xi\xi} u \pm \left(2k_y \mp \frac{1}{\xi} \right) \partial_\xi u + F^2 \xi^2 u = 0. \quad (13)$$

The presence of the term $F^2\xi^2u$ leads to a power series significantly far from the other terms due to the ξ^2 factor. We can fix this issue by introducing another substitution $u(\xi) = g(\xi)\exp(\pm iF\xi^2/2)$, which resembles the solution derived for the case $k_y = 0$ corresponding to the Eq. (48) later in section III B, and where “+” is for the **K** valley while “-” is for the **K'** valley. The resulting equation then becomes:

$$\partial_{\xi\xi}g \pm \left(2iF\xi + 2k_y \mp \frac{1}{\xi}\right) \partial_{\xi}g + 2ik_yF\xi g = 0. \quad (14)$$

To simplify Eq. (14), we introduce new parameters: $\mu = 2k_y$, $\nu = 2iF$, and $\lambda = 2ik_yF$ which yields to a modified equation:

$$\partial_{\xi\xi}g \pm \left(\nu\xi + \mu \mp \frac{1}{\xi}\right) \partial_{\xi}g + \lambda\xi g = 0. \quad (15)$$

We emphasize that in Eq. (15), the condition $F \neq 0$ guarantees that both ν and λ are non-zero.

The series expansion using the power series method becomes applicable now. By defining $g(\xi) \equiv S = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \xi^n$, we obtain:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n n(n-1) \xi^{n-2} \pm \left(\nu \xi \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n n \xi^{n-1} + \mu \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n n \xi^{n-1} \mp \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n n \xi^{n-2} \right) + \lambda \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n \xi^{n+1} = 0. \quad (16)$$

After several derivations, we modify the dummy summation variable n to k in each power series and convert the ξ exponents into new summation variables:

$$-\frac{a_1}{\xi} \pm \mu a_1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [a_{k+2}(k+2)k \pm \nu a_k k \pm \mu a_{k+1}(k+1) + \lambda a_{k-1}] \xi^k = 0, \quad (17)$$

where we gathered the non-zero terms and grouped all summations starting from $k = 1$. It becomes clear that the equation is satisfied when we set $a_1 \equiv 0$, and all the terms within the square bracket $[\dots]$ sum up to zero. This condition implies the following recurrence relation between the coefficients a_{k+2} :

$$a_{k+2} = \mp \frac{\mu(k+1)}{k(k+2)} a_{k+1} \mp \frac{\nu}{k+2} a_k - \frac{\lambda}{k(k+2)} a_{k-1}. \quad (18)$$

Alternatively, we can revert to using the summation variable n that leads to the following recurrence relation:

$$a_n = \mp \frac{\mu(n-1)}{n(n-2)} a_{n-1} \mp \frac{\nu}{n} a_{n-2} - \frac{\lambda}{n(n-2)} a_{n-3}, \quad (19)$$

where $n = 3, 4, \dots$, and the upper and lower signs correspond again to the **K** and **K'** valleys, respectively. Since $a_1 \equiv 0$, we have only two unknown coefficients remaining, namely, a_0 and a_2 .

By separately collecting the power series terms involving a_0 and a_2 , we can divide the entire series into two distinct special functions represented by $R(\xi, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda)$ and $V(\xi, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda)$ similar to how the Airy functions² serve as solutions to the triangular potential well. However, neither these special functions R and V nor their derivatives are Airy functions as we shall see later. Each of these R and V functions is designated by a power series with coefficients determined from the recursive relation in Eq. (19) and from two specific initial conditions. Specifically, we set $a_0 = 1$ and $a_2 = 0$ for the R -function, while for the V -function, we set $a_0 = 0$ and $a_2 = 1$. The general solution of Eq. (14) can then be expressed in the form:

$$g(\xi) = C_1 R(\xi, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda) + C_2 V(\xi, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda), \quad (20)$$

where $C_{1,2}$ represent the arbitrary constants to be determined from the boundary conditions. Essentially, these constants indicate the free parameters a_0 and a_2 .

Now, we can write down the general solution for Eq. (12) explicitly as:

$$\phi_B(\xi) = \exp(\pm k_y \xi) \exp\left(\pm \frac{iF\xi^2}{2}\right) [C_1 R(\xi, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda) + C_2 V(\xi, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda)], \quad (21)$$

where the upper “+” and lower “-” signs correspond to the **K** and **K'** valleys, respectively. Applying the boundary conditions from Eq. (12) where $\phi_B(\xi_1) = \phi_B(\xi_2) = 0$ and $\xi_{1,2} = (\varepsilon/F) \pm (L/2)$, we get the following relations of coefficients C_1 and C_2 :

$$C_1 = -C_2 \frac{V(\xi_1, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda)}{R(\xi_1, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda)}, \quad (22)$$

$$C_1 = -C_2 \frac{V(\xi_2, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda)}{R(\xi_2, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda)}. \quad (23)$$

Substituting this coefficient relation in Eq. (22) gives us a general equation of ϕ_B :

$$\phi_B = C_2 \exp(\pm k_y \xi) \exp\left(\frac{\pm iF \xi^2}{2}\right) M(\xi) \quad (24)$$

where $M(\xi)$ is defined in terms of the special functions R and V :

$$M(\xi) \equiv [R(\xi_1, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda) V(\xi, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda) - R(\xi, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda) V(\xi_1, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda)] / R(\xi_1, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda) \quad (25)$$

As for the spinor component ϕ_A , we recall that $\phi_A = \frac{1}{i\xi F} (\partial_x \phi_B \mp k_y \phi_B)$ with the upper “−” and lower “+” signs indicating the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' valleys, respectively. The spinor ϕ_A -component expressed in terms of special functions R and V is then:

$$\phi_A = \frac{C_2}{iF\xi} \exp(\pm k_y \xi) \exp\left(\pm \frac{iF \xi^2}{2}\right) [\partial_\xi \pm iF\xi] M(\xi) \quad (26)$$

where the upper “+” and lower “−” signs correspond to the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' valleys, respectively. Combining Eqs. (24) and (26), and then normalizing the full expression yield the normalized spinor Ψ solution represented by:

$$\Psi = \begin{pmatrix} \phi_A \\ \phi_B \end{pmatrix} = C \exp(\pm k_y \xi) \exp\left(\pm \frac{iF \xi^2}{2}\right) \exp(ik_y y) \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{iF\xi} \partial_\xi M(\xi) \pm M(\xi) \\ M(\xi) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (27)$$

where the normalizing constant C is given by:

$$C = \left(\sqrt{\int_{\frac{\varepsilon}{F} - \frac{L}{2}}^{\frac{\varepsilon}{F} + \frac{L}{2}} \exp(\pm 2k_y \xi) \left[\left| \frac{1}{iF\xi} \partial_\xi M(\xi) \pm M(\xi) \right|^2 + |M(\xi)|^2 \right]} \right)^{-1} \quad (28)$$

and the function $M(\xi)$ is defined in Eq. (25) with the special functions R and V , and the upper “+” and lower “−” signs correspond to the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' valleys, respectively. It is important to note here that

$$\phi_B \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{F} + \frac{L}{2} \right) = \phi_B \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{F} - \frac{L}{2} \right) = 0 \iff M(\xi_1) = M(\xi_2) = 0. \quad (29)$$

The homogeneous system of linear equations given by Eqs. (22) and (23) has non-trivial solutions only when the determinant of its matrix equals zero, which then leads to a dispersion equation:

$$\exp\left(\frac{iF(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2)}{2}\right) M(\xi_2) R(\xi_1, \pm\mu, \pm\nu, \lambda) = 0. \quad (30)$$

For a given F and L , Eq. (30) establishes the connection between ε and k_y . One can retain the complex exponent in Eq. (30), since it serves as a regularizing factor which ensures that the zeros of the dispersion equation are determined solely by its real part.

III. DISCUSSION

In this section, we shall investigate some limiting cases of the above-described problem for the Dirac equation with the boundary conditions in Eq. (6). The zero-energy modes (ZEMs) of the Dirac fermions shall be explicitly shown with a single k_y -point solution to the two-component spinor Ψ function. Finally, we shall present the unique properties of R and V special functions in a form of complex plots and distinguish these two functions from the well-known Airy functions.

A. Bulk modes

The Eqs. (9) and (10) in the case $F = 0$ reads

$$-i\partial_x \phi_B \pm ik_y \phi_B = \varepsilon \phi_A, \quad (31)$$

$$-i\partial_x \phi_A \mp ik_y \phi_A = \varepsilon \phi_B, \quad (32)$$

where k_y is the electron momentum along the ribbon measured with respect to the Dirac point and the upper and lower signs of $\sigma_y k_y$ identify the \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' valleys, respectively. We want to find the secular equations from these two set of differential equations. Expressing ϕ_A from Eq. (31) as $\phi_A = -(i/\varepsilon)\partial_x\phi_B \pm (ik_y/\varepsilon)\phi_B$ and putting it into Eq. (32), we arrive at a single second order equation:

$$-\partial_{xx}\phi_B + k_y^2\phi_B = \varepsilon^2\phi_B. \quad (33)$$

The general solution of Eq. (33) is $\phi_B = C_1e^{zx} + C_2e^{-zx}$, with $z = \sqrt{k_y^2 - \varepsilon^2}$ and $C_{1,2}$ as constants determined from the boundary and normalization conditions. We use the boundary conditions (6):

$$\phi_B\left(-\frac{L}{2}\right) = \phi_B\left(+\frac{L}{2}\right) = 0 \quad (34)$$

which yield the following set of equations:

$$C_1e^{z(-L/2)} + C_2e^{-z(-L/2)} = 0, \quad (35)$$

$$C_1 = -C_2e^{zL},$$

$$C_1e^{zL/2} + C_2e^{-zL/2} = 0, \quad (36)$$

$$2e^{-zL/2}C_1 \sinh(zL) = 0.$$

Eq. (36) shows that the secular equation $\sinh(zL) = 0$ leads to $\varepsilon = \pm |k_y|$. However, this solution is spurious since then ϕ_B is identically vanishing because of $z = 0$. The correction description around zero-energy is shown in the next section.

Another approach is to substitute $z = ik_x$ that leads to quantization of the transverse electron momentum k_x : $k_x = \pi n/L$, with n being integer. The valence and conduction energy bands are described by $\varepsilon = \pm\sqrt{k_y^2 + (\pi n/L)^2}$, where $n = \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$. Then Eqs. (34) take form:

$$C_1e^{-ik_xL/2} + C_2e^{ik_xL/2} = 0, \quad (37)$$

$$C_1e^{ik_xL/2} + C_2e^{-ik_xL/2} = 0.$$

These homogeneous set of linear equations from Eq. (37) can have non-trivial solutions when the determinant is zero, which defines the quantization of k_x . From the second equation in Eqs. (37), we get $C_2 = -C_1e^{ik_xL}$ so that $\phi_B = -2iC_1e^{ik_xL/2} \sin[k_x(L/2 - x)]$ and $\phi_A = \pm 2C_1e^{ik_xL/2} \cos[k_x(L/2 - x) + \varphi]$, where '+' and '-' in ϕ_A are used for the bands above and below $\varepsilon = 0$, respectively, and $\varphi = \arcsin(k_y/\sqrt{k_y^2 + k_x^2})$. Thus, the normalized spinor is:

$$\Psi = \begin{pmatrix} \phi_A \\ \phi_B \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \begin{pmatrix} \pm \cos[k_x(L/2 - x) + \varphi] \\ -i \sin[k_x(L/2 - x)] \end{pmatrix}, \quad (38)$$

where the global phase $e^{ik_xL/2}$ is ignored. It is seen from Eq. (38) that the obtained spinor describes extended or bulk states.

B. Zero-energy edge mode

The zero-energy modes (ZEMs) of Dirac fermions have been interesting subject in quantum field theory since its first introduction by Jackiw and Rebbi⁴⁵ in 1976. Currently, ZEMs play pivotal role in topological phases of condensed matter⁴⁶. We encounter a ZEM by considering Eq. (7) in the \mathbf{K} -valley for $F = 0$:

$$(-i\sigma_x\partial_x - \sigma_y k_y)\Psi = \varepsilon\Psi, \quad (39)$$

where $\Psi = (\phi_A, \phi_B)^T$. We set $\varepsilon = 0$ and multiply both sides by σ_x to find:

$$\partial_x\Psi = -\sigma_z k_y\Psi. \quad (40)$$

If the spinor Ψ is an eigenvector of σ_z , that is, $\sigma_z V_\lambda = \lambda V_\lambda$, then the Eq. (40) above reduces to a scalar equation where for $\lambda_+ = 1, V_+ = (1, 0)^T$ and for $\lambda_- = -1, V_- = (0, 1)^T$. Then, the $\Psi_\lambda = V_\lambda \chi(x)$, where the scalar function $\chi(x)$ is found from:

$$\partial_x\chi(x) = -\lambda k_y\chi(x). \quad (41)$$

From the solution $\chi_{\pm}(x) = A \exp(-\lambda_{\pm} k_y x)$, the spinors can be described with:

$$\Psi_{\pm}(x) = V_{\pm} A \exp(-\lambda_{\pm} k_y x), \quad (42)$$

where they exponentially change for $k_y \neq 0$. These spinors are similar to those combined to construct a normalizable Jackiw-Rebbi soliton⁴⁵ satisfying the boundary conditions $\Psi_{\pm}(x \rightarrow \pm\infty) \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$. Our boundary conditions given in Eq. (6) are different. Therefore, we need to pick out only one spinor out of two provided by Eq. (42), the one that satisfies the boundary conditions in Eq. (6). Here, we do not need a combination of spinors in order to produce a normalizable solution since our system has finite size along x -axis. Considering the finite size of the system, the counterpart of the Jackiw-Rebbi soliton emerges as a fully sublattice polarized mode. Evidently, the arbitrary constant in the general solution of the first-order Eq. (41) corresponds solely to the normalization degree of freedom. Thus, the appropriate solution is

$$\Psi_{+}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} C_1 \exp(-k_y x). \quad (43)$$

We can find the normalization constant as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \Psi_{+}^{\dagger}(x) \Psi_{+}(x) dx &= 1, \\ |C_1|^2 \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \exp(-2k_y x) dx &= 1, \\ |C_1| &= \sqrt{\frac{k_y}{\sinh(k_y L)}}, \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

which allows us to write down the ZEM normalized spinor:

$$\Psi_{+}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \sqrt{\frac{k_y}{\sinh(k_y L)}} \exp(-k_y x). \quad (45)$$

Varying k_y around the Dirac point ($k_y = 0$) shifts the ZEM wave function from one edge to another while preserving sublattice polarization and maintaining its chiral nature. The ZEM wave function loses its localization only at the proximity of the Dirac point. The wave function in Eq. (45) is an eigenfunction of the 2×2 chiral symmetry operator $\mathcal{S} = \sigma_z$.

The second spinor in Eq. (42) satisfies boundary conditions $(I + \sigma_z) \Psi|_{x=\pm L/2} = 0$ [cf. Eq. (6)]. Physically, this means imposing condition on A sublattice. The A sublattice counterpart of Eq. (45) reads:

$$\Psi_{-}(x) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \sqrt{\frac{k_y}{\sinh(k_y L)}} \exp(k_y x). \quad (46)$$

In the 2×2 Dirac equation $i\partial_t \Psi = H\Psi$, where H is defined by Eq. (39), the hole (or charge conjugation) symmetry operator is denoted as $\Xi = \sigma_x K$ with K representing the complex conjugation. Upon applying the Ξ operator to Ψ_{\pm} as described in Eqs. (45) and (46), it is evident that $\Xi \Psi_{\pm} \neq \Psi_{\pm}$ which indicates that the identified ZEM does not conform to Majorana fermion properties. The solutions in the \mathbf{K}' valley are essentially the same and can be obtained from those above via substitution: $k_y \rightarrow -k_y$.

C. Field independent $k_y = 0$ states ladder and 1+1 chiral anomaly structure

Equation (12) has a much simpler analytic solution at the Dirac point, $k_y = 0$, where we obtain

$$\partial_{\xi\xi} \phi_B - \frac{1}{\xi} \partial_{\xi} \phi_B + F^2 \xi^2 \phi_B = 0, \quad (47)$$

for both \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' , resulting in the solution space described by:

$$\phi_B(\xi) = C_1 \cos\left(\frac{F\xi^2}{2}\right) + C_2 \sin\left(\frac{F\xi^2}{2}\right). \quad (48)$$

Such simple solution allows to find analytical expressions for energy levels, which form an equidistant ladder that is independent of the field F . The two boundary conditions from Eq. (6) together with Eq. (48) lead to a set of simultaneous equations:

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 \cos\left(\frac{F\xi_1^2}{2}\right) + C_2 \sin\left(\frac{F\xi_1^2}{2}\right) &= 0, \\ C_1 \cos\left(\frac{F\xi_2^2}{2}\right) + C_2 \sin\left(\frac{F\xi_2^2}{2}\right) &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

The set of Eqs. (49) has non-zero solutions for coefficients C_1 and C_2 only if the determinant of the set matrix is zero. This condition then defines the dispersion equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos\left(\frac{F\xi_1^2}{2}\right) \sin\left(\frac{F\xi_2^2}{2}\right) - \sin\left(\frac{F\xi_1^2}{2}\right) \cos\left(\frac{F\xi_2^2}{2}\right) &= 0, \\ \sin\left[\frac{F}{2}(\xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2)\right] &= 0, \\ \sin(\varepsilon L) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

where we have substituted the definitions of ξ_1 and ξ_2 in the last line. Solving Eq. (50), a set of field-independent energy states $\varepsilon = \pi n/L$ is found for $n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$, which includes also a zero-energy state.

The state pinned at zero energy for any value of F together with the note made after Eqs. (9) and (10) reveals the 1 + 1 chiral anomaly structure of the energy levels upon $F \neq 0$. Indeed, when $|k_y| \rightarrow \infty$, we have $\alpha(x) = \varepsilon + Fx = 0$, so that Eqs. (9) and (10) become of the same type as those in section III B. Namely, they result in the exponentially localized edge states, therefore we can set $x = \pm L/2$ in $\alpha(x)$. Hence, in general $\varepsilon = \pm FL/2$. Recall, however, that \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{K}' -valley spinors are localized at opposite edges, thus $\varepsilon = \pm FL/2$ in \mathbf{K} -valley and $\varepsilon = \mp FL/2$ in \mathbf{K}' -valley in the case $|k_y| \rightarrow \infty$. To summarize, as k_y changes from $-\infty$ to ∞ , the energy band labeled with $n = 0$ changes from $\varepsilon = FL/2$ to $-FL/2$ passing through zero when $k_y = 0$. The picture is reversed in the \mathbf{K}' -valley. This behaviour of $n = 0$ energy bands exhibiting a gauge field dependent chiral anomaly structure is schematically shown in Fig. 1(b).

D. Functions R and V

To distinguish functions R and V from the Airy functions, we first examine the recurrence relations given by Eq. (19) compared to those of the Airy functions. From the Airy equation $y'' - zy = 0$, the recurrence relations are

$$a_{n+2} = \frac{a_{n-1}}{(n+2)(n+1)}, \quad (51)$$

where $a_2 \equiv 0$. The closest we can get to it is by setting in Eq. (18) $\mu = \nu = 0$ and $\lambda = -1$:

$$a_{k+2} = \frac{a_{k-1}}{(k+2)k}, \quad (52)$$

but even in this case we have $a_1 \equiv 0$ and denominator $(k+2)k$ instead of $(n+2)(n+1)$ from the recurrence relations of the Airy functions. In Fig. 2(a), we compare $V(z, 0, 0, -1)$ function with the Airy function of the second kind $Bi(z)$ by plotting their complex plots. It is clearly seen that while zeros represented by hue vortices are positioned differently, they follow the same C_3 symmetry within the complex plane. Similar regularity is observed for R function and the Airy function of the first kind $Ai(z)$, when $\mu = \nu = 0$ and $\lambda = -1$.

Explicitly showing the first few terms in the power series representation (not to be mixed with the Taylor expansion) of Airy functions and R and V :

$$Ai(z) = 1 + \frac{z^3}{(3 \cdot 2)} + \frac{z^6}{(6 \cdot 5)(3 \cdot 2)} + \dots, \quad (53)$$

$$Bi(z) = z + \frac{z^4}{(4 \cdot 3)} + \frac{z^7}{(7 \cdot 6)(4 \cdot 3)} + \dots, \quad (54)$$

$$R(z, \mu, \nu, \lambda) = 1 - \frac{\lambda z^3}{3} + \frac{1}{8} \lambda \mu z^4 + \frac{\lambda}{15} \left(\nu - \frac{\mu^2}{2} \right) z^5 + \dots, \quad (55)$$

$$V(z, \mu, \nu, \lambda) = z^2 - \frac{2\mu z^3}{3} + \frac{1}{4} (\mu^2 - \nu) z^4 + \frac{1}{15} \left(-\lambda - 4\mu \left(\frac{\mu^2}{4} - \frac{\nu}{4} \right) + 2\mu\nu \right) z^5 + \dots, \quad (56)$$

we can see some similarities and differences between our R and V functions and the Airy functions. The power series of R function has a missing z^2 term, while V function is missing 1 term. These are linearly independent monomials. The power series of $Ai(z)$ is missing z term, while $Bi(z)$ is missing 1 term. Globally, Airy functions are missing z^2 terms and all dependent ones as follows from Eq. (51): $0 = a_2 = a_5 = a_8 = \dots = a_{3n+2}$. In contrast, R and V -functions are generally missing z terms in their power series representation. When $\mu = \nu = 0$, it follows from Eq. (52) that the series of missing terms is $0 = a_1 = a_4 = a_7 = \dots = a_{3n+1}$ for both R and V .

We note here that our definition of the Airy functions, stated above in Eqs. (53) and (54), is different from those given in some mathematical literature (see, for instance, Sec. 10.4 in Ref.⁴⁷). In the notations presented in Ref.⁴⁷, our Airy functions $Ai(z)$ and $Bi(z)$ should be denoted as $f(z)$ and $g(z)$, respectively.

Finally, we present the complex plots of R and V based on selected values of their intrinsic parameters μ , ν and λ , see Fig. 2(b,c). We make the most obvious choice for the parameter values: 0, 1, and i . A notable observation here is the presence of a double zero at the origin for all the graphs of the V function compared to the R function and Airy functions.

IV. CONCLUSION

In summary, the Dirac equation for a confined massless fermion coupled to a gauge field, which is motivated by the eigenproblem of a half-bearded GNR under an external in-plane electric field, can be analytically solved using new R and V special functions. These functions are defined as power series, with coefficients determined recursively through Eq. (19). Similar to the Jackiw-Rebbi soliton in 2D⁴⁵, the zero-energy modes of the given Dirac equation exhibit $1 + 1$ chiral anomaly favorable for scattering-free currents and highly sought for in the condensed matter physics within the context of topological phases of matter. As a striking contrast to other $1 + 1$ chiral anomalies^{48,49}, the chiral anomaly structure here exhibit a gauge field dependence, and therefore it is finely tunable. It is remarkable to observe that the configuration of the gauge field aligns with the potential current flow in the Hall effect: the field in our case is perpendicular to the transport direction. This perpendicular configuration suggests reversibility between the anomaly and its inflow^{50,51}, but further research is needed in this direction. We suggest additional investigation into the formal aspects of this anomaly as a quantum field anomaly.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that supports the findings of this study are available within the article.

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FIG. 2. (a) A comparison between R and V functions and Airy functions of the first $Ai(z)$ and second $Bi(z)$ kind. Multiple zeros and phase patterns are distributed following C_3 symmetry, i.e. three rays starting at the origin and forming $2\pi/3$ angles between them. (b) Complex plots of R function for selected values of the inherent parameters μ , ν and λ . (c) Same as (b) but for V function. In all plots, the cyclic color function is used for the argument of the complex number ranging from $-\pi$ to π represented by hue color change from blue to green via red for a zero phase ("CyclicLogAbsArg" option as defined in Wolfram Mathematica); The color function goes from $-\pi$ (blue) to 0 (red) to π (green) counterclockwise around zeros, and clockwise around poles.

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